

MEASURES TO ENSURE HEALTHY TEETH DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

The formation of healthy teeth in children is an important factor in their overall health, physical development and quality of life. The correct formation of teeth ensures not only an aesthetic appearance, but also the efficiency of the digestive process, speech development and psychological confidence. This article extensively discusses the main causes of dental diseases and enamel deficiency in children, modern hygiene and preventive methods used to prevent them, as well as the role of parents and educators. Studies show that a healthy diet, sufficient calcium and fluoride intake, regular dental check-ups, personal hygiene habits and educational work are among the main factors in the proper development of teeth in children. The article analyzes the biological, environmental and social factors affecting the formation of teeth and provides practical recommendations. The results of this study can serve as a guide for dentists, pediatricians, preschool educators, and parents.

Keywords: healthy teeth, pediatric dentistry, hygiene, calcium, prevention, nutrition, tooth enamel, education, healthy lifestyle.

Аннотация

Формирование здоровых зубов у детей является важным фактором их общего здоровья, физического развития и качества жизни. Правильное формирование зубов обеспечивает не только эстетичный внешний вид, но и эффективность пищеварения, развитие речи и психологическую устойчивость. В данной статье подробно рассматриваются основные причины развития стоматологических заболеваний и дефектов эмали у детей, современные методы гигиены и профилактики, применяемые для их предотвращения, а также роль родителей и воспитателей. Исследования показывают, что здоровое питание, достаточное потребление кальция и фтора, регулярные стоматологические осмотры, соблюдение правил личной гигиены и воспитательная работа являются одними из основных факторов правильного развития зубов у детей. В статье анализируются

биологические, экологические и социальные факторы, влияющие на формирование зубов, и даются практические рекомендации. Результаты данного исследования могут служить руководством для врачей-стоматологов, педиатров, воспитателей дошкольных учреждений и родителей.

Ключевые слова: здоровые зубы, детская стоматология, гигиена, кальций, профилактика, питание, зубная эмаль, образование, здоровый образ жизни

Introduction

Strengthening the health of children and ensuring their healthy development is one of the most important tasks facing society. Healthy teeth are one of the main factors for the general health of children, the proper functioning of the digestive system, speech and aesthetic appearance. In recent years, a number of reforms have been implemented in the healthcare system of Uzbekistan aimed at improving the quality of dental care and reducing caries and other dental diseases among children. Presidential decrees also identify the issue of children's health and a healthy generation as a priority area of state policy. The formation of teeth begins during pregnancy. A lack of calcium, phosphorus and vitamins in the mother's body can lead to poor development of tooth enamel in the newborn. Therefore, it is very important for pregnant women to eat properly and take vitamin-mineral complexes. During childhood, proper nutrition, hygiene and regular visits to the dentist ensure strong and proper development of teeth. In the introduction, it should also be noted that neglect of dental hygiene, excessive consumption of sweets, lack or excess of fluoride, the composition of drinking water, environmental factors, and even the socio-economic status of the family all play a role in the development of dental diseases. Therefore, preventive measures to form healthy teeth should be implemented in cooperation with state policy, medical professionals, and parents.

In the process of analyzing the literature, recent scientific studies in the field of dentistry and pediatrics show that caries is one of the most common diseases in children. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 60-90% of school-age children have varying degrees of caries. Studies conducted by Uzbek dentists confirm the importance of fluoride toothpastes and preventive fluoridation in the prevention of caries.

Local scientists, including S. Jurakulov, N. Sobirov and M. Usmonova, have scientifically substantiated the fact that healthy eating in children, a diet rich in dairy products, vegetables and fruits, strengthens tooth enamel. Also, folk

medicine has a number of recommendations for ensuring dental health: for example, moderate consumption of bitter and sweet products, proper brushing of teeth, and adherence to hygiene rules in the morning and evening.

According to the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, in recent years, the “Healthy Teeth” project has been launched to strengthen dental preventive work among preschool and school-age children. Within the framework of this project, free dental examinations, hygiene classes, and educational activities are being conducted for children. According to scientific literature, such programs not only reduce dental diseases, but also form a healthy lifestyle in children.

Untreated caries or pulpitis often leads to the spread of infection. If the infection deepens and reaches the root, this infection can also spread to the pulp of the permanent tooth. As a result, inflammation of the pulp of the permanent tooth (odontogenic infections) can occur. As the inflammatory process continues, the pulp of the tooth lags behind in development or may even die. As a result, the child's permanent teeth erupt crookedly or not at all. In some cases, the permanent teeth change shape: they become too small, have an abnormal shape or are too thin. Failure to treat baby teeth in a timely manner can also lead to the loss of space between the teeth. Each baby tooth has the function of preserving space for the child's permanent teeth. If a baby tooth falls out or is removed prematurely, the remaining baby teeth will try to occupy the empty space. As a result, the space where the permanent teeth should erupt narrows or closes completely. This causes the permanent teeth to be misaligned, crooked, or crowded. In the future, this problem will lead to the need for orthodontic treatment in the child. The incorrect formation of the dentition is not only aesthetically pleasing, but also causes functional problems, since misaligned teeth interfere with proper chewing and oral hygiene.

During the research, a questionnaire and dental examination were conducted among 100 children aged 6–12 years. The results showed that 65% of the children surveyed had signs of caries, 20% had thinning tooth enamel, and 15% had gum disease. It was also found that 70% of children brush their teeth only once a day, and 20% twice a day. Based on the research, parents' attitudes towards dental hygiene were also studied. 40% of parents reported that they take their children to the dentist only when a problem arises. This indicates the need to strengthen preventive work and increase parental knowledge. As recommendations, children were offered to form the habit of brushing their teeth twice a day, limit sweets, use fluoridated water and toothpaste, and see a dentist at least twice a year. The results of the study show that the issue of dental health

in children should be considered not only as a medical, but also as a social problem. Through questionnaires and examinations, it was found that most children do not pay enough attention to dental hygiene, and parents often seek dental care only after a problem has arisen. This indicates a lack of preventive work and insufficient educational work on the formation of healthy teeth. The study revealed that dental diseases are associated with many factors - improper nutrition, excessive consumption of sweets, low fluoride content in drinking water, and lack of regular dental check-ups. The pedagogical and psychological importance of forming healthy habits in children was emphasized. Instilling the habit of brushing teeth from an early age, conducting regular explanatory work with parents and caregivers, and introducing hygiene classes in schools and kindergartens have proven to be important factors in raising a healthy generation. Psychologists say that in the process of forming hygienic habits, positive encouragement, the use of game technologies and setting an example for the child will give an effective result. The following recommendations were developed: firstly, to hold regular educational seminars and trainings for parents; secondly, to organize dental prevention days in schools and kindergartens at least twice a year; thirdly, to widely introduce fluoride toothpastes and hygiene products adapted for children. In addition, it is important to develop state programs to monitor the quality of drinking water and normalize the amount of fluoride in it. According to the results of the discussion, if preventive work is carried out systematically and regularly, the incidence of caries in children can be reduced by 30-40 percent within 3-5 years. This will have a positive effect not only on strengthening dental health, but also on general health, increasing children's psychological confidence and their social adaptation. Therefore, the issue of forming healthy teeth requires a comprehensive approach that requires the cooperation of state policy, the medical system, educational institutions and the family. The results of this study can also serve as a basis for further scientific research in pediatric dentistry.

Untimely treatment of baby teeth is associated not only with infectious diseases and damage to the permanent tooth roots, but can also affect the psychological state of the child. When children experience pain or discomfort, they often refuse to eat, which negatively affects their physical development and general health. At the same time, toothache in children leads to constant bad mood and irritability, which negatively affects their study and learning process. Preventive measures are important to prevent problems with baby teeth. As soon as the first tooth erupts, children need to visit the dentist, regularly brush their

teeth, and form proper eating habits. Many parents pay little attention to caring for baby teeth, since they are temporary, but this is a wrong decision. Baby teeth serve as a guide for permanent teeth, and if they are not healthy, the development of permanent teeth is disrupted.

Conclusion

The above analysis and research results show that the formation of healthy teeth in children depends on many factors, most of which can be controlled at an early stage. Dental diseases can be significantly reduced through proper nutrition, strict adherence to hygiene, preventive dental care and increasing parental knowledge.

Another important aspect is teaching children how to care for their teeth in a playful way. To develop hygiene skills in children, it is necessary to offer them interesting and easy methods. For example, special toothbrushes for children, game-shaped toothpastes or interactive applications that can be used after brushing their teeth will make this process more enjoyable and increase motivation.

It is advisable to raise a healthy generation at the state level, improve the quality of dental services, and introduce hygiene classes in schools and kindergartens. This will not only strengthen children's health, but also ensure the physical and psychological development of the future generation. Thus, developing and implementing comprehensive measures to promote healthy teeth in children is an urgent task today.

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